

**INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM IN CLOUD COMPUTING USING
ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK WITH CUCKOO SEARCH APPROACH**Poonam verma^{*1}
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In recent years, with the increasing popularity of cloud computing, security in the cloud has become an important topic. The detection and blocking of attacks is better compared to responding attacks after the system is threatened. Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is an important part of maintaining network security. Also, with the rapid development of cloud platforms it's getting more and more popular in our daily life, it's very useful, and required to build valid IDS for the cloud. However, existing intrusion detection technologies will might be faced challenges when deploying on the cloud platform. This paper proposed a secure cloud environment for the cloud application user using an integrated approach of nature inspired Cuckoo Search (CS) with Artificial neural Network (ANN) approach. Here, CS is used to select the best properties of the nodes and then used as an input data to the ANN structure. ANN algorithm helps to safeguard cloud framework from the attacks.

Keywords:

Cloud Computing, Intrusion Detection System, Cuckoo Search, and Artificial Neural Network.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, more and more people are used an extra space on the basis of pay per use because of their advantages such as high scalability, high elasticity and low operating cost [1]. Cloud service users generally don't need to know how a cloud-based application or platform works; instead, they should only send requests to the cloud provider and wait for their results, which is an easier and more efficient way to access the required computing resources [2]. Although present cloud platform suffers from several problems. According to (Okuhara et al; 2010), the cloud safety problems like leakage of data, unauthorized access to confidential data are the two major issues faced by cloud user [3].

In some web applications, like as online retailing/ auctions, network security has become a major factor in the Internet age. The Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is used to protect system from the external as well as from the internal threats based on the data record. IDS is mainly categorized into two types named as anomaly and misuse detection [4]. The aim of Anomaly detection system is to segregates the normal data from the intrusion based on their specific deviation and then flagged out or block it from the system. In misuse detection system, the pattern of attack is already known before its identification. To solve intruder problem in cloud becomes a hard NP problem and can be resolved by a number of researchers based on different evolutionary and machine learning approaches [5].

Cloud Computing Environment

Cloud Computing is one of the internet based and growing technology in the world. Using this technology, the resources such as: software, memory, platform and information are shared by the clients on demand basis. It is a dynamically scalable scheme in which virtualized resources are offered to the cloud user via web. Since, the user's have not buy physical infrastructure, therefore, the cost has been saved. The user rent the resources from the cloud providers, use them and pay only for those resources that they have used [6].

Three fundamental models for Cloud Computing are:

- i. Software as a Service (SaaS)
- ii. Platform as a Service (PaaS)
- iii. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)

The SaaS model is used to provide quick services of cloud based web applications. The cloud user manages the whole computing stack that is accessed by the cloud user though web browser. These services are utilized by the cloud user either by getting subscription or for free with limited access [7].

In IaaS model, the computing resources are used through virtualization scheme over cloud. This service helps the user to provide a complete computing infrastructure like as storage, servers and other hardware needed for maintenance and support.

In PaaS model, the a platform is provided to the users in which one can develop, test as well as organize distinct applications for client's business [8].

Figure 1 Layered architecture of cloud computing [9]

Intrusion Detection

Early detection of threat is an event tracking process of a computer system or network. Intrusion is defined as an unauthorized attempt to the available resources, which completed by compromising on confidentiality, integrity or availability override your computer or network or security mechanisms.

In traditional enterprise systems, IDS is typically deployed on particular hardware at the edge of the network infrastructure which is to be protected from external attacks. In a cloud computing environment, this strategy will not be successful and effective when on-demand, on a pay-per-use basis, sharing computing and communication resources across multiple users have been used. Therefore, an appropriate defense strategy needs to be properly allocated in the cloud so that it can detect and block user-initiated attacks originating from the cloud itself and also using cloud technologies from different geographic locations over the Internet. In this research, the cloud resources are protected using ANN as a deep learning approach [10]

RELATED WORK

In this section, few papers related to the presented work has been studied, Also, the classification algorithms of machine learning schemes used by a number of researchers for detecting abnormality in the cloud environment has been discussed. The classification approach gather data from other networks and train the system based on the features of data.

Hajimirzaei et al. (11, 2019) have presented a secure cloud computing system from intruder by designed a IDS using ABC with Fuzzy clustering approach. multilayer preceptor has been trained based on normal and abnormal data traffic, which is obtained after applying Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) approach to the input data. The results have been computed in terms of Mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), and the kappa statistic.

Sakr et al. (12, 2019) have presented an anomaly based detection system to monitor and observe the network traffic flow. An integration of optimization with classification schemes such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) with Support Vector (SVM) has been used. PSO has been utilized to select an appropriate feature set of network nodes. Based on these feature set value SVM has been trained and later used for identification of unauthorized access. The

Moustafa et al. (13, 2017) have presented a two-way anomaly detection model for identifying cyber attack in cloud environment. The model has been designed or trained using UNSW-NB 15 dataset while worked with the cloud environment. The performance has been measured in terms of false positive and detection rate. In the given dataset, the data has been categorized into different categories that consist of one normal and other nine abnormal types of security events. The experiment shows that the detection rate and false positive rate up to 95.6 % and 3.5 % has been achieved.

Wang et al. (14, 2018) have used correlation analysis with principle component analysis technique to solve the problem of complex scale, processing and transfer of large amount of data in cloud framework. Using correlation analysis, the similarities between distinct metrics and the running status of the system has been identified. After that PCA has been applied to determine the anomaly degree and also to predict the fault prediction.

Nawir et al. (15, 2019) have employed supervised machine learning approach for the detection of threat with minimum communication cost and bandwidth by using UNSW-NB15 database. The performance has been measured in the form of accuracy and processing time. The labeling of the dataset has been performed using machine learning approach and the accuracy up to 97.26 % with a minimum processing time of 7 s has been achieved.

Deshpande et al. (16, 2018) have presented a host based intrusion identification structure for cloud environment. The threat has been identified by monitoring the system calls regularly. Using this approach the burden on cloud for computing unnecessary operations has been minimized. For the identification of threat KNN is used as a classifier that is to distinguish between the normal and abnormal system call traces. The results indicate accuracy of about 96 %.

METHODOLOGY

This section comprises of flow of work, in which, the work has been carried out along with the detail description of techniques used. IDS model has been presented that comprises of number of nodes working based on ANN approach on the cloud environment. From the designed, it is predicted to obtain better flexibility, scalability with better performance.

Proposed Work

Initially, a cloud network is designed with a defined length and height and nodes are deployed along with their coordinate positions. After deploying nodes, a source node with the destination node has been defined. Now, the data communication between the source node and the destination node has been performed by transmitting data. The nodes properties of the cloud users: such as normal and abnormal are provided as input data to the input layer of the ANN structure. The input data is processed by the input layer and then passed to the hidden layer as shown in figure 2. In hidden layer a biased weight is added to the input data, which modifies the data as per the requirement and then forwarded the processed data to the output layer of the ANN structure. If an error signal appears at the output layer then it is feedback to the input layer to adjust the data so that the error signal is minimized up to the desire. In this way the cloud system is trained using ANN scheme, which was later used to segregate normal and abnormal data and hence secure the system.

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Figure 2 ANN Structure

The output of neurons in the hidden layer is calculated on the basis of;

$$Z_j(P) = \text{sigmoid} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i(p) \times w_{ij}(p) - \theta_j] \quad (1)$$

N represents the number of input neurons with j number of hidden layer and sigmoid as a activation function, which is given by;

$$S = 1 + \frac{1}{e^{-s}}$$

e → base of natural logarithm

CS with ANN Algorithm for Anomaly Detection

Required Input:	T ← Training Data as server properties
	C ← Target/Category
	N ← Number of Neurons
Achieved Output:	AS ← Anomaly Server

1 Start

3 Set up basic parameters of CSA: Population of Egg (E) – Number of Properties

OT – Optimized Training Data

$$\text{Fitness Function: } F(f) = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{if } S_p < \text{Threshold}_p \\ 0; & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where, S_p : It is properties of current server which are in T and

Threshold_p : It is the threshold properties of all servers on the basis of energy consumption

4 Calculate Length of T in terms of R

5 Set, Optimized Training Data, OT = []

6 For i in rang of R

7 $C_{Egg} = FR(i) = S_p$ // Current Egg from E

8 $T_{Egg} = \text{Threshold}_p$ // // Current Egg

9 $F(f) = \text{Fit Fun}(C_{Egg}, T_{Egg})$

10 $Ses_{prop} = \text{CSA}(F(f), FR(i))$

11 End

12 Initialize ANN on the basis of T, C and N

13 Set, Cloud-Net = Newff (T-Data, T_R , N)

14 Cloud-Net.TrainParam.Epoch = 1000

15 Cloud-Net.Ratio.Training = 70%

16 Cloud-Net.Ratio.Testing = 15%

17 Cloud-Net.Ratio.Validation = 15%

18 Cloud-Net = Train (Cloud-Net, T-Data, T_R)

19 Current Server = Properties of current server in Cloud-Net

20 Authentication = simulate (Cloud-Net, Current Server)

21 **If Authentication = True**

22 Genuine Server not consider in AS

23 **Else**

24 AS = Anomaly Server

25 **End**

26 **Return:** AS a list of Anomaly Server

27 **End**

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A number of experiments have been conducted to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed IDS in cloud system. During experiment, 50 numbers of nodes (server machines) are deployed using MATLAB (Matrix laboratory) as a simulator, with a laptop having about 20 GB RAM, Quad core i3 processor and 500 GB of hard disk. The performance has been observed based on the following parameters.

Accuracy: the accuracy of the proposed work has been evaluated using TNR (True Negative Rate) and FPR (False Positive rate).

The TNR is given as:

$$TNR = \frac{\text{The count of sequence judged abnormal in the abnormal dataset} - \text{abnormal}}{\text{Total number of normal and abnormal count in the given dataset}}$$

$$FPR = \frac{\text{The count of sequence judged abnormal in the normal dataset} - \text{abnormal}}{\text{Total number of normal and abnormal count in the given dataset}}$$

Table 1: Computed Parameters

Number of iterations	TNR	FPR	Accuracy
1	85	9	96.87
2	87	8	96.98
3	89	10	96.84
4	90	5	97.87
5	92	7	97.69
6	94	8	97.95
7	91	9	98.58
8	93	8	98.87
9	96	7	99.87
10	95	8	99.65

The examined value of TNR and FPR are illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively. X-axis and y axis represents the number of iterations and the evaluated parameters such as TNR and FPR respectively. From figure 3, it is very much clear that with the increase in the number of iteration, the TNR has been increased up to 6th iteration and after that decreases at 7th iterations. The reduction in TNR is appears due to the increase in the number of unwanted features or the abnormal data during the communication process between cloud user and cloud providers. The average of TNR obtained for the proposed work is 91.2 % respectively.

The FPR measured for the proposed work using ANN technique is shown in Figure 4. It represents the falsely detected abnormal data from the normal dataset and from the figure it is seen that about 7.9 % of data has been detected falsely. This rate is very less and hence enhances the accuracy rate up to 98.117 % as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 3: TNR of Proposed Work

Figure 4: FPR of Proposed work

Figure 5: Accuracy of proposed Work

Also, to show the effectiveness of the proposed work, the comparison between proposed and existing work performed by Cheng et al. in 2018 has been examined. The comparison graph related to TNR, FPR and accuracy is shown in the figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively.

Figure 6: Comparison of TNR

The comparison of TNR performed by the ANN algorithm and with the Chen et al work is shown in Figure 6. From the graph it is clearly seen that the TNR i.e the rate of detecting abnormal data or attacker using proposed work is higher compared to the existing work. The enhancement of about 0.44 % has been achieved using ANN approach.

Figure 7: Comparison of FPR

Figure 7 demonstrated the comparison of FPR of the proposed work with the Chen et al. work during the anomaly detection in cloud environment. The average value of FPR determined with the proposed and the Chen et al. work is represented by the blue color and the red color respectively. There is a reduction of about 21 % has been observed compared to the existing Chen et al work.

Figure 8: Comparison of Accuracy

The comparison of accuracy parameter is shown in Figure 8. The average value of accuracy in contrast to the Chen et al. work has shown in Figure 8. The figure shown an enhancement in the accuracy rate compared to the existing work by 0.12 %.

CONCLUSION

Today, user behavior anomaly detection of data streams has attracted considerable interest in many areas, but this poses a huge challenge for researchers. In this paper, we have proposed an ANN based anomaly detection model for the identification of anomaly behavior of data stream. The cloud network has been trained based on the normal and abnormal properties of nodes using ANN as a machine learning approach. The ANN helps to enhance the accuracy rate as well as decrease the human effort. The experimental results demonstrated that the TNR and accuracy rate has been increased by 0.44 % and 0.12 % respectively. Also, there is a reduction of about 21 % has been observed in the FPR of the proposed work. In future, the work can be extended by using any optimization algorithm with the ANN approach. The optimization approach helps to obtain best nodes properties and thereafter resulting in better training set using ANN approach. This will enhance the performance of the proposed cloud system with better accuracy.

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